

PSYCHOLOGICAL AND PHYSIOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF CHARACTER.

Rakhimova Feruza

is a teacher of the Kokan State Pedagogical Institute.

Madaminjonova Fatimakhan

No'monjonova Maftunakhan

Holdarova Yulduzkhan

Students of the Kokan State Pedagogical Institute

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Abstract: the article presents psychological and physiological data of the character and the theories of scientists, along with this information is given about the characteristics of the character in the development of the individual.

Key words: Character, features, personality, environmental psychology, physiology.

Each person differs from any other person by his individual - psychological characteristics. It's about character. The word "character" literally means "mark" from the Greek. Character is a set of individual-psychological characteristics that are considered typical for this person, manifested in the methods of activity, visible in typical conditions and determined by the attitude of the person to these conditions. Manifestation of character traits - individual characteristic of emotional experiences of each typical situation depends on personal relationships. On the other hand, qualities of action and individual specific methods in each typical situation depend on personal relationships. Intellectual, emotional and volitional qualities of character can be distinguished. By character, we understand the individual characteristics that are formed in a person under the influence of environment and upbringing and are manifested in his volitional activity, in his relations with the surrounding world (other people, work, things).

A lot of character traits are deep and active inclinations that determine a person's actions. It is in these inclinations that the persuasive power of character traits is manifested. Due to such a compelling force of character traits, a person often acts contrary to objective conditions and uses methods of action that are completely incompatible with the goal. Some people knowingly choose a difficult task, some do the opposite. As character traits encourage to act in a certain way and sometimes to act against the circumstances, they are better manifested in difficult moments of life. Character is tested in the struggle against opposing conditions. Character education is one of the central and important tasks of raising a mature generation. Persistence includes qualities such as

critical vision, understanding, observation, alertness - intellectual (mental), cheerfulness, kindness - emotional - volitional characteristics.

Physiological foundations of the character, as it is known, the type of nervous system depends on the innate features of higher nervous activity. However, a person's physiological nature does not remain constant. I.P. Speaking about the relationship between the type of the nervous system (temperament) and the character, Pavlov wrote: "The type of animal nervous activity, the type of innate organism, is genetic - but from the day the animal is born, the environment is different. due to the fact that it must inevitably respond to these influences with activity that often remains stable throughout life, it consists of a combination of the characteristics of the existing type of nervous activity of the animal and the changes required by the external environment, phenotype, character ".

Although I.P. Although Pavlov spoke about animals, humans also feel the same effects of the environment. It should be remembered that not only the I signal system, but also the II signal system has a great influence on the formation of human nervous activity. Thus, although the innate type of the nervous system is the basis of the temperamental character, it is determined by the characteristics of temporary nervous connections and their complex systems, which a person acquires in the course of his life and work. The appearance of emotions, mental processes, and the speed of movement mainly depend on temperament, which is certainly reflected in the character of a person. As a result, not innate qualities, but social conditions, that is, the influence of the environment, is the main reason why a person has this or that character. Moral qualities of character, such as diligence, honesty, truthfulness, kindness, initiative, humility; Volitional qualities of character, such as striving for a goal, determination, courage, bravery, tenacity, self-control.

It is formed depending on the conditions of a person's life, changing and being educated: in special conditions, under the influence of special education and upbringing, it is possible to eliminate negative character traits and cultivate positive character traits. Personality relationships determine the individual characteristics of character traits in 2 different ways. On the one hand, the individual characteristics of the emotional experiences of each typical situation in which this characteristic of the character is manifested depends on the relationship of the person. In addition, the ways of human character depend on the characteristics of will, mood, attention, and thinking. For example: diligence

and thoroughness in work depends not only on a positive attitude to work, but also on concentration of attention, accuracy of actions, willpower, and so on. Therefore, it is possible to distinguish intellectual-emotional and volitional qualities of character depending on the dominant influence of various mental processes on the methods of action.

To conclude, as we mentioned above, each person is a unique irrevocable world. It is very difficult to find two people who are exactly alike in the world. A person may look like someone else in appearance, height, but in terms of their actions, behavior, and personality, they are not exactly the same. Scientists have even found that twins developed from the same egg are very similar in many respects, and some differences have been identified in the correlation of their personal qualities.

The personality is irrevocable, it is unique in that it has its own qualities. At the basis of this irreversibility and uniqueness lies a set of his individual psychological characteristics. At this point, we consider it appropriate to comment on two other concepts that are used side by side with the concept of the person given above. These are the concepts of "individual" and "individuality". The concept of "individual" complements the concept of "man" in general and confirms its existence as a social and biological being.

As they say, the family is a small country, the role of the family in the formation of a child's character is very important. Family environment and interaction of parents and treatment of children. We can see it in the form of a child who grew up in conflict situations or grew up under excessive pampering.

In conflict situations, we can see cases of extreme arrogance, tyranny, and bitterness in a child who grows up in conflict situations.

Such people are quarrelsome, do not trust anyone, are cold-hearted and achieve everything by their own strength, and will not suffer anything in the way of their goal.

A boy who grew up in extreme masculinity reaches school age and even when he goes to school, he is very manly among his peers, tries to do what he says in a manly and critical manner. And such people will struggle to get out of a difficult situation on their own in the future, and it will be difficult for them to achieve something.

From this we can see that it is good that everything is in order.

Seeing that everything depends on the family, why do we take education so lightly now? After all, we are human beings, conscious beings, and this is the difference between us and animals. We need to understand that this situation,

which seems to be hopeless for us, will be a bad influence of our children's education in the future, and we should prevent this sad situation.

It is no exaggeration to say that psychology is a solution to such problems.

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